

Emergence of Equal Cooperation Induced by Characteristics of Adolescence than Adulthood in an Interrole Conflict Game among Reinforcement Learning Agents

Takashi Sato

Abstract: People usually belong to multiple groups, and in such situations "interrole conflicts" occur. Studies on interrole conflicts have mainly targeted subjects after adulthood, although they do not occur only after the developmental stage of adulthood. In addition, limited studies have been conducted on interrole conflicts during adolescence. Furthermore, simulation studies about interrole conflicts have rarely been conducted. The purpose of this study is to clarify the difference between adolescence and adulthood in how to deal with interrole conflict situations. We propose an interrole conflict game (ICG) as a new game-theoretic framework to deal with interrole conflicts and adopt reinforcement learning agents with characteristics of adolescence or adulthood as players. Our multi-agent simulation (MAS) experiment results suggest high learning rate and low discount rate that cause typical adolescent characteristics including risk-taking, impulsivity and novelty seeking can be played important roles to cope an interrole conflict and for emergence of equal cooperation among adolescents in the interrole conflict situation.

Keywords: interrole conflict game (ICG), reinforcement learning, multi-agent simulation (MAS), characteristics of adolescence or adulthood, emergence of equal cooperation.

I. INTRODUCTION

People usually belong to multiple groups, and in such situations "interrole conflicts" may occur. As shown in Fig. 1, an interrole conflict is a conflict that occurs when people belonging to multiple groups are requested to work simultaneously by those groups [1-2]. This causes various problems, such as deterioration of mental health [3]. Therefore, it is extremely important to elucidate the various patterns of interrole conflicts and the characteristics of how to deal with them.

Fig. 1 An interrole conflict situation where work is being requested from a person belonging to many groups simultaneously.

In addition, interrole conflicts take place frequently in places where people belonging to multiple groups gather, regardless of generation or roles. Consequently, interrole conflicts do not occur only after the developmental stage of adulthood. Nonetheless, studies on interrole conflicts have mainly targeted subjects after adulthood. Furthermore, there have been limited studies on interrole conflicts during adolescence that occur within schools or between schools and homes.

Adolescence, the period between childhood and adulthood, is the time to form an ego identity and build the mental and physical foundations for life after adolescence. In addition, adolescents have the behavioral characteristics of being prone to dangerous and impulsive problem behaviors [4-5]. Serotonin, a neurotransmitter in the brain, is involved in adolescent impulsivity [6]. It was pointed out that low serotonin concentration was associated with emotional irritability and irritation [7]. It is also known that the adolescent brain has high plasticity that dynamically changes the brain, such as synapses, neurons, and axons [8-10]. Konrad *et al.* [11] suggested that typical adolescent characteristics, which included risk-taking, could be caused by high plasticity of the adolescent

Corresponding Author: Takashi Sato. Department of Media Information Engineering, National Institute of Technology, Okinawa College, 905, Henoko, Nago, Okinawa, 905-2192, Japan
Tel: +81-980-55-4179, Fax: +81-980-55-4012, E-mail: stakashi@okinawa-ct.ac.jp

brain. Furthermore, in the adolescent brain, the cerebral limbic system that controls emotions develops and matures rapidly. In contrast, the prefrontal cortex, which suppresses impulsive behavior and plays an important role in executing plans in a proper order, matures in early adulthood. The inability of adolescents to perform actions in an orderly and systematic manner is thought to be due to the immaturity of their prefrontal cortex. It was also found that differences in the degree of development of these brain regions caused behavioral characteristics peculiar to adolescence [12].

As mentioned above, adolescents have different characteristics from adults. Hence, they experience various types of conflicts along with interrole conflicts. Adolescence is an important developmental stage that establishes an independent self and forms the mental and physical foundations of life through the experience of various conflicts. Therefore, focus only on adulthood to elucidate the emergence and transformation process of coping strategies for alleviating interrole conflicts that cause various problems is not enough. Furthermore, a structural and mechanical understanding of dynamics during development from adolescence to adulthood is essential.

Therefore, we must prepare multiple populations organized by dividing human subjects according to their adolescent characteristics. It is also necessary to continue to conduct "interaction" experiments under interrole conflict situations inside and outside those populations until adulthood. However, such an experiment is difficult to conduct even with a small number of people and groups.

When such large-scale experiments with human subjects are difficult, a Multi-Agent Simulation (MAS) experiment can show its true potential. However, there are almost no studies concerning interrole conflicts targeting both of adolescents and adults using the MAS.

Based on these, the core question of this study is: How do behaviors in interrole conflict situations differ between adolescents and adults? Hence, this study aims to answer the above question using the MAS that consists reinforcement learning agents with adolescent or adult characteristics.

Elucidating these questions may lead to the solution of interrole conflicts that arises even after adulthood. This is also extremely important in pursuing good physical, mental and social conditions, namely, well-being.

II. INTERROLE CONFLICT GAME

A. An interrole conflict expressed by game-theoretic framework

As shown in Fig. 1 mentioned above, an interrole conflict is a conflict that occurs when the people belonging to multiple groups are requested to work by those groups simultaneously. To express this interrole conflict situation as a game-theoretic framework, the following three conditions must be met: 1) people belonging to multiple groups, 2) they can cooperate with only one group at a time, and 3) they can benefit by the cooperation from others except for themselves. However, there is no game that meets all three conditions. Therefore, we propose an interrole conflict game (ICG) with the above three characteristics as a new game that expresses the situations of interrole conflicts.

Figure 2 shows a schematic diagram of the minimum configuration of ICG when the number of players and groups are three, respectively and the maximum number of groups to which each person can belong is two. In this study, we adopt the ICG with this minimum configuration, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 A schematic view of the minimum configuration of an interrole conflict game (ICG) where the number of players and groups are three, respectively and the maximum number of groups to which each person can belong is two.

Players of the ICG can get three types of rewards as follows: 1) 1 is given when $S > 1$, 2) 0 is given when $S = 1$, and 3) -1 is given when $S < 1$, where S is the bare minimum number of cooperative people in a group, R^+ is a positive reward, and R^- is a negative reward. The sum of rewards reaped from all groups to which the player belonged is given to the player. For example, in case of the Fig. 2, the player-A who belongs to both of the group-1 and 2 gets " R^++R^- ," the player-B who belongs to both of the group-2 and 3 gets " $0+R^-$," and the player-C who belongs to both of the group-1 and 3 gets " R^++0 ."

Based on the reward function, the optimal solution in the ICG with the minimum configuration is to rotate in turn in three groups that the two players cooperate in each group.

B. Reinforcement learning agents with characteristics of adolescence and adulthood as players of the ICG

We adopted reinforcement learning agents as the players of the task and Q-learning [13-14] as the learning method. Q-learning [13-14] is a reinforcement learning method by trial and error. In accordance with the following (1), the agents with the Q-learning renew their Q-values, which represent the worth of the agents' actions for each state of the environment and obtain more appropriate behaviors.

$$Q(s(t), a(t)) := Q(s(t), a(t)) + \alpha[r(t+1) + \gamma \max_a Q(s(t+1), a) - Q(s(t), a(t))] \quad (1)$$

where $a(t)$ is an action conducted at time t , $Q(s(t), a(t))$ is a Q-value for an action conducted under a state s at time t , α is the learning rate, $r(t+1)$ is a reward given from the environment when conducting an action under a state s , and γ is the discount rate. The ϵ -greedy policy [13-14] was adopted as the method of selecting actions.

In the ICG, each player selects one group to which they belong as a group that cooperates by themselves every step. The actions of the players are identical with the number of groups to which they belong. The states that are necessary to select an action are the group numbers that were selected by all players at the time t .

Differences of characteristics of adolescence and adulthood can be represented by settings of the learning and the discount rates in the reinforcement learning agents. We interpret that the plasticity of brain is expressed by the learning rate, and the discount rate in the reinforcement learning corresponded to the serotonin, a neurotransmitter in the brain. Therefore, the adolescent with high plasticity and low concentration of the serotonin can be represented by the reinforcement learning agent with high learning rate and low discount rate. By contrast, the adult with low plasticity and high concentration of the serotonin can be represented by the one with low learning rate and high discount rate.

III. RESULTS

A. Settings of the simulation experiments

The parameters of the ICG simulation experiments were set as listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Settings of the simulation experiments.

The maximum number of steps	1,000,000
The number of players (agents)	3
The number of groups	3
The number of groups to which one player can belong	2
The bare minimum number of cooperation in a group S	1
The rewards R^+ and R^-	+1 and -1
The learning rate α	11 paterns = {0.01, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 0.99}
The discount rate γ	11 paterns = {0.01, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 0.99}
The degrees of randomness ϵ in action selection for the ϵ -greedy policy	11 paterns = {0.0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1.0}

The MAS experiments of the ICG use each setting independently as shown in the Tables 1 and are conducted every twenty different random seeds.

B. Results of the simulation experiments

First, we confirm that the average numbers of cooperation each group in case two players are gathered to one group. To compare with a MAS experiment that consists of three reinforcement learning agents, we determine a baseline of such numbers by using complete random players with no learning. As seen in Fig. 3, the baseline of the average numbers of cooperation is approximately 250,000.

Fig. 3 The average numbers of cooperation in each group in case two players are gathered in one group earned by the MAS experiment that consists of three complete random players. The baseline of cooperation number is approximately 250,000.

Fig. 4 The average numbers of cooperation in each group in case two players are gathered in one group earned by the MAS experiment that consists of three players per different parameters.

Fig. 5 The average numbers of cooperation in three groups in case two players are gathered in one group earned by the MAS experiment that consists of three players per different parameters in detail. Green circles indicate the peak numbers of cooperation in each column γ , orange circles show the ones for each row α , and light blue circles illustrate the ones that meet the condition that becomes the maximum on both of row and column.

Fig. 4 shows the average numbers of cooperation in each group in case two players are gathered in one group by using the MAS experiment that consists of three players per different parameters. Due to a space of constraint, we show the results in case of $\epsilon = 0.1, 0.3$ and 0.5 , and $\alpha = 0.01, 0.5$ and 0.99 , and $\gamma = 0.01, 0.5$ and 0.99 .

As the degree of randomness when selecting an action; namely, ϵ is increased, the average numbers of cooperation moved to close to the results by the complete random players, and influence from α and γ decreased. When α is extremely small (such as 0.01), as γ increase, the number of cooperation increase. However, the cooperation among three players become

unstable, as seen from the length of bars that express the standard deviations of the number of cooperation in these figures. As α increase to an extent, the number of cooperation also increase, and achieve a peak when α is 0.6, and γ is 0.01. As α increase from 0.6, the number of cooperation decrease gradually.

Next, by illustrating the heatmaps of the average number of cooperation in each group confirmed by the MAS experiments with all parameters, we summarized the differences of influences of all parameters, such as ε of the ε -greedy policy, the learning rate α and the discount rate γ on the emergence of cooperation. Due to a space of constraint, we show the results in case of $\varepsilon = 0.1, 0.3$ and 0.5 .

As seen in Fig. 5, we find that the reinforcement learning agents as the ICG players realize more cooperation than the baseline made by the complete random players. However, as ε increase, the number of cooperation moves to close to the one earned by the complete random players gradually. Then, although the case of $\varepsilon = 0.9$ was left out in this paper, we confirmed that the result with $\varepsilon = 0.9$ was almost the same the one earned by the complete random players.

In Fig. 5, green circles indicate the peak numbers of cooperation in each column γ , orange circles show the ones for each row α , and light blue circles illustrate the ones that meet the condition that becomes the maximum on both of row and column. As seen, in most cases where γ is 0.01, the numbers of cooperation became the peak whenever α is set to any values. As γ increases from 0.01 to 0.99, it is necessary to decrease α from approximately 0.7 for the peak of cooperation to emerge.

IV. DISCUSSION

We discuss the results showed in our simulations from the viewpoint of the relations between parameters of the reinforcement learning and our brains. We focused on the learning rate α and discount rate γ as important parameters of reinforcement learning.

The learning rate α was a parameter to determine the amount of updating the action value. If the learning rate α was large, the agent drastically changed their action value according to the reward received. However, an agent with a small learning rate α hardly changed their action value. In our brain, acetylcholine, a neurotransmitter, is suggested to play an important role as a gate signal that decides whether to keep past memories or exchange it for new ones [15]. The learning rate α can be said to be corresponded to acetylcholine. It is also known that, compared to adult brains, adolescent brains have high plasticity that

dynamically changes their brains, including synapses, neurons, and axons [8-10]. Konrad *et al.* [11] suggest that there is a possibility that typical adolescent behavior patterns, which include risk-taking, are caused by the high plasticity of the adolescent brain.

Based on these suggestions, we presume that agents with high learning rates, can be regarded as adolescents with high plasticity, can change their actions rapidly, easily showed cooperation in the ICG. The players who can rapidly change their action values according to immediate rewards when they can judge their actions are bad win an advantage over players who cannot in the ICG, as it is a game where it is difficult to predict even near future results. In fact, our simulation results showed that the agents with high learning rate and low discount rate achieved a greater number of equal cooperation than the ones with low learning rate and high discount rate.

The discount rate γ was a parameter to determine which immediate and delayed rewards were emphasized. As the brain learns, related to the discount rate, Okamoto *et al.* [16] showed that serotonin played an important role in controlling a time scale parameter for reward prediction. Therefore, the discount rate γ could be regarded as representing serotonin. Furthermore, Miyazaki *et al.* [17-18] clarified that, in a delayed reward task using rats, increasing flow rate of serotonin and activating the serotonin nervous system was related to waiting for the delayed reward. Their experimental results [17-18] can be interpreted as that there were two modes of the discount rates in which a large γ gave high praise to delayed reward, however, a small γ did not do so, and the two modes were switched by the amount of serotonin. Agents with high discount rates had high expectations for expected rewards. In a highly volatile ICG where there was no guarantee that other individuals would continue to cooperate with the same group, this agent would be less dependent on expected rewards by having a low learning rate. As a result, it was thought that relatively equal cooperation could be maintained.

V. CONCLUSION

We noted that there were few studies on interrole conflict in adolescence. Hence, this study aimed to clarify the difference between adolescence and adulthood in dealing with interrole conflict situations. To accomplish the purpose, we have proposed an "interrole conflict game (ICG)" as a new game-theoretic framework that represented the situation of interrole conflict. Furthermore, as players in the ICG,

we adopted the reinforcement learning agents that had characteristics of adolescents or adults.

Although our proposed ICG and the reinforcement learning agents adopted as players of the ICG are models omitted many things such as influences by environments and human emotions, our simulation experiment results suggested that high learning rate and low discount rate that caused typical adolescent characteristics, which included risk-taking, impulsivity and novelty seeking, played important roles to cope with interrole conflict and to emerge an equal cooperation among people in the interrole conflict situation.

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